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Geopolitics and Genocide: How Major Powers Limit Recognition and Response

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Abstract

This paper critically examines the influence of geopolitical interests on the international response and recognition of genocides, with a focus on the Armenian Genocide, the Rwandan Genocide, and the Gaza crisis. Through these case studies, it is demonstrated that major powers frequently misuse their veto power in the United Nations Security Council to protect their allies, thereby undermining international law and humanitarian principles. This analysis underscores the realist critique of liberal internationalism, highlighting that state power and interests predominantly drive international relations. The findings indicate that the selective application of veto power and the protection of strategic allies by major powers have significantly hindered effective international intervention and accountability in cases of genocide. The study advocates for a robust international framework that aligns global governance with humanitarian principles to protect vulnerable populations and ensure lasting peace and justice.

Keywords: Geopolitical Interests, Genocide Recognition, Major Powers, Gaza Crisis, International Law

Introduction

In recent years, the term ‘genocide’ has resurfaced with heightened relevance among researchers and analysts, especially given the escalating fatalities, destruction, and humanitarian crisis in Palestine. Israel's military actions have led international organizations to label the situation as genocide or potential genocide. However, major powers, particularly the United States, vehemently reject such proclamations, defending Israel's actions as self-defence. This dichotomy is not novel; it reflects a long-standing pattern where major powers undermine the recognition and

response to genocides in global politics. This pattern is evident in the current Israel-Palestine conflict, where the United States has used its veto power multiple times to block ceasefire resolutions, despite significant human casualties and widespread destruction. The United States' strategic alliance with Israel highlights how geopolitical interests often trump humanitarian considerations. This misuse of veto power by major powers illustrates a broader issue: the manipulation of international law to serve national interests, often at the expense of justice and human rights.

The influence of geopolitical interests on the response to genocides can be traced back to historical events such as the Armenian Genocide and the Rwandan Genocide. During the Armenian Genocide, geopolitical alliances and the focus on World War I prevented timely intervention and recognition. Major powers, including the United Kingdom, France, and Russia, were preoccupied with their military campaigns, which overshadowed humanitarian concerns. Similarly, the United States maintained a stance of neutrality, influenced by isolationist policies and diplomatic complexities, delaying recognition and intervention (Balakian, 2004). The Rwandan Genocide further exemplifies how geopolitical interests can limit international responses. Despite clear evidence of mass atrocities, major powers, including the United States and France, were reluctant to intervene. The United States, wary of involvement after the failed mission in Somalia, and France, with its strategic interests in Rwanda, prioritized national interests over humanitarian action. The UN peacekeeping mission, UNAMIR, was under-resourced and constrained by a weak mandate, leading to a failure to prevent the genocide (Power, 2002; Melvern, 2000). The ongoing Gaza crisis is a contemporary case that underscores the same troubling dynamics. The United Nations and various international organizations have indirectly declared the situation a genocide, while the United States, a key ally of Israel, rejects these claims. This stark contrast highlights how the term 'genocide' is often politicized, with major powers using their influence to shape international responses according to their strategic interests.

This paper provides a comprehensive analysis of these issues by examining the Armenian Genocide, the Rwandan Genocide, and the Gaza crisis. It argues that the actions of major powers have significantly hindered the international community's ability to respond effectively to

genocides. The manipulation of international law for geopolitical gains not only obstructs justice but also emboldens genocidal regimes to act with impunity. By dissecting these case studies, this paper sheds light on the critical need for reform in international mechanisms to ensure that humanitarian principles are upheld. It advocates for limiting the veto power in cases of genocide and human rights violations and emphasizes the importance of major powers exercising accountability over their allies. Such reforms are essential to align global governance with humanitarian goals, protect vulnerable populations, and promote lasting peace and justice.

Genocide: Definition, History and Legal Framework

The term 'genocide' was coined by the Polish-Jewish lawyer Raphael Lemkin in 1944. Lemkin introduced this term in his seminal work, 'Axis Rule in Occupied Europe,' in which he sought to describe the systematic destruction of national, ethnic, racial, and religious groups. The word 'genocide' combines the Greek word 'genos' (meaning race or tribe) and the Latin suffix 'cide' (meaning killing), thus encapsulating the concept of group extermination. Lemkin's interest in crimes against groups stemmed from his early exposure to atrocities, particularly the Armenian Genocide of 1915, which profoundly influenced his thinking. His motivation was further fuelled by the horrors of the Holocaust during World War II, where the Nazis systematically murdered six million Jews, along with millions of others, including Romani people, disabled individuals, and political dissidents. Lemkin's tireless advocacy was crucial in bringing the concept of genocide to the forefront of international law. He believed that the destruction of a group, whether national, ethnic, racial, or religious, was a crime that needed distinct recognition and stringent prevention measures. His efforts culminated in the adoption of the term 'genocide' by the international community and its eventual codification into international law (Lemkin, 1944, 1-10).

Genocide was formally identified as a crime under international law by the United Nations General Assembly in 1946 through Resolution 96-I. This recognition was further solidified in 1948 with the adoption of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide, commonly referred to as the Genocide Convention. This convention established genocide as an independent crime and provided a legal framework for its prevention and punishment. As of April 2022, the Convention has been ratified by 153 states.¹ Article II of the Genocide Convention

defines genocide ‘as any of the following acts committed with intent to destroy, in whole or in part, a national, ethnical, racial, or religious group: killing members of the group; causing serious bodily or mental harm to members of the group; deliberately inflicting on the group conditions of life calculated to bring about its physical destruction in whole or in part; imposing measures intended to prevent births within the group; and forcibly transferring children of the group to another group’ (Bloxham & Moses, 2010, 123-124). The Genocide Convention establishes that the crime of genocide can occur in both armed conflict and peaceful situations, though the latter is less common.

Throughout history, several instances of genocide have occurred, each marked by systematic attempts to destroy specific groups based on their national, ethnical, racial, or religious identities. These atrocities have left indelible marks on the global conscience and have often been met with varied international responses influenced by the political interests of major powers. The Armenian Genocide of 1915-1923, perpetrated by the Ottoman Empire, resulted in the deaths of an estimated 1.5 million Armenians. Despite overwhelming evidence and survivor testimonies, recognition of this genocide has been contentious (Joe, 2017, 137-155). The Cambodian Genocide (1975-1979), carried out by the Khmer Rouge regime under Pol Pot, led to the deaths of approximately 1.7 million people through starvation, forced labour, and execution (Ben, 2012). The Rwandan Genocide of 1994 saw the brutal killing of around 800,000 Tutsis and moderate Hutus in a span of 100 days. The international community, including major powers and the United Nations, faced heavy criticism for their failure to prevent or halt the genocide (Peter, 2001, 75-99). The Bosnian Genocide (1992-1995), which occurred during the breakup of Yugoslavia, involved the systematic killing of Bosniaks (Bosnian Muslims) by Bosnian Serb forces. The Srebrenica massacre in 1995, where over 8,000 Bosniak men and boys were killed, was a stark example of genocide. Despite the presence of United Nations peacekeeping forces, the international response was criticized for being insufficiently robust, influenced by the political complexities of the Balkans and the strategic interests of European powers and the United States (Amerasinghe, 2008, 443). In the case of the ongoing conflict in Gaza, allegations of genocide and war crimes have similarly been influenced by geopolitical interests. Major powers, particularly the United States, have consistently rejected

the characterization of the situation in Gaza as genocide, citing Israel's right to self-defence against aggression from Hamas and other militant groups.²

While the legal framework for addressing genocide has evolved significantly since Raphael Lemkin's pioneering work, the recognition and response to genocides remain heavily influenced by the geopolitical interests rather than by the application of international organisations or by law. This manipulation has often resulted in delayed recognition, inadequate responses, and, in some cases, complete denial of genocides. The interplay between international law and geopolitical considerations continues to shape the global community's ability to effectively prevent and punish the crime of genocide, underscoring the need for sustained advocacy and robust international mechanisms to uphold the principles enshrined in the Genocide Convention.

Genocide and the Geopolitics of Major Powers

Genocides continue to persist in the modern world, largely due to the failure of what realists call liberal internationalism. Liberal internationalism, grounded in the belief that international organizations and global governance can effectively resolve conflicts and promote peace, has largely failed in both areas, particularly in preventing genocide. Realists argue that international relations are anarchic in nature, where the role of international organizations and law is limited. What truly matters is the power to survive in this anarchic international system (Hoffman, 1995, 163). This perspective is crucial in the context of genocide, as powerful states still dominate international organizations and often violate international ethics. For instance, permanent members of the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) have frequently misused their veto power to serve their own interests, whether in wars or in blocking resolutions aimed at stopping ethnic violence (Mearsheimer, 2001, 47-48). This failure is predominantly attributed to the violation of international laws by major powers in pursuit of their national or geopolitical interests. The active policies of these powers and their misuse of veto powers have significantly undermined the efficacy of international law on genocide. This has, in effect, provided a free hand to other states or actors to commit acts of genocide. The inefficacy of international law, as evidenced by these actions, underscores the realist critique of liberal internationalism and suggests a victory for realist principles in global politics (Waltz, 1979).

International law, particularly regarding genocide, is meant to protect human rights and ensure justice. The Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1948, was a landmark in this regard. However, the enforcement of these laws has been hampered by the political interests of powerful nations. Major powers have frequently violated these laws, using their influence and veto powers within international organizations to shield themselves and their allies from accountability. This has created a culture of impunity, where states or actors committing genocide can do so without fear of significant repercussions (Abbot, 1999, 365). For instance, the veto power held by the five permanent members of the UNSC – the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Russia, and China – has been a critical factor in this failure. These nations have used their veto power to block actions against genocidal regimes, thereby protecting their geopolitical interests (Trahan, 2020). For instance, Russia and China have consistently used their veto power to shield the Syrian regime from international sanctions and interventions, despite credible evidence of mass atrocities and war crimes (Weiss, 2018, 149-150). Similarly, the United States has often shielded Israel from international censure regarding its actions in Palestine (Chomsky, 2015, 50).

The misuse of veto power by permanent members of the United Nations Security Council significantly undermines the principles of international law and weakens the effectiveness of international organizations like the United Nations. This practice sends a message to other states and non-state actors that they can commit acts of genocide without facing significant consequences, provided they have the backing of a powerful ally. As a result, there has been a notable failure to prevent genocides and hold perpetrators accountable, highlighting the limitations of liberal internationalism (Barnett, 2002; Weiss, 2018; Chomsky, 2015). This misuse or limitation posed by major powers on immediate humanitarian response and recognition of genocide can be analysed through three important case studies: the Armenian Genocide, the Rwandan Genocide, and the current debate on the Gaza crisis. In each of these cases, the response of the international community has been significantly hindered by the geopolitical interests of major powers.

Case Studies on the Geopolitical Influence of Major Powers in the Recognition and Response to Genocide

1. Armenian Genocide

The Armenian Genocide during World War I, where 1.5 million Armenians were systematically exterminated by the Ottoman Empire, highlights the impact of geopolitical interests on both immediate humanitarian responses and long-term recognition of genocidal acts. Major powers, particularly the Allied Powers (United Kingdom, France, and Russia), were deeply focused on military campaigns against the Central Powers, including the Ottoman Empire, which overshadowed humanitarian concerns. Despite issuing a joint declaration in May 1915 condemning the Ottoman government for its 'crimes against humanity and civilization,' the Allied Powers did not take concrete actions to stop the genocide due to resource constraints and strategic priorities (Hovannisian, 1992, 43-47).

The United States, maintaining a stance of neutrality for much of the war, refrained from decisive action due to isolationist policies and diplomatic complexities. Recognition and intervention came too late, only after the extensive damage had been done (Balakian, 2004, 315-317). Post-war, geopolitical considerations continued to influence the recognition of the Armenian Genocide. During the Cold War, Turkey's strategic importance as a NATO ally bordering the Soviet Union led to Western reluctance to officially recognize the genocide, fearing it would jeopardize vital geopolitical alliances (Winter, 2003, 147-149). Turkey has persistently denied the genocide and used its diplomatic leverage to prevent international recognition, influencing the stance of many countries and international organizations (Akçam, 2006). This selective memory and political expediency in international politics underscore the limitations of liberal internationalism in preventing and responding to genocides. The Armenian Genocide case demonstrates how international relations, driven by power and survival, often neglect justice and humanitarian principles, supporting the realist critique that international law is limited by the self-interests of major powers (Smith, 2008, 58-60).

2. Rwanda genocide

The Rwandan Genocide of 1994, where 800,000 Tutsis and moderate Hutus were killed in 100 days, exemplifies how geopolitical interests of major powers have limited both immediate humanitarian response and long-term recognition of genocidal acts. The major powers, particularly the United States, France, and the United Kingdom, lacked the political will to intervene, with the U.S. wary of involvement after the failed mission in Somalia (Power, 2002, 330, 335, 359). The UN peacekeeping mission, UNAMIR, was under-resourced and constrained by a weak mandate, despite warnings from its commander, General Roméo Dallaire (Barnett, 2002, 147-148). France's Operation Turquoise, aimed at humanitarian intervention, was criticized for protecting the genocidal regime due to France's strategic interests in Rwanda (Melvern, 2000).

During the genocide, the international community avoided labelling the atrocities as 'genocide' to evade obligations under the Genocide Convention, delaying effective response (Kuperman, 2001, 110). The International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) faced challenges like limited funding and political pressure, impacting its efficacy (Mamdani, 2001). Additionally, selective memory and political expediency influenced long-term recognition and justice, with insufficient scrutiny of the international community's failures (Des Forges, 1999, 623-625). The Rwandan Genocide highlights the failure of liberal internationalism in the face of major powers' geopolitical interests. The inadequate response and selective recognition underscore the realist critique that international relations are driven by power and survival, often at the expense of humanitarian principles.

3. Gaza Crisis

The Gaza crisis exemplifies how geopolitical interests of major powers limit immediate humanitarian response and recognition of genocidal acts. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict, particularly in Gaza, has seen significant violence and humanitarian crises, with major powers playing crucial roles. Since 2008, the conflict has resulted in over 5,000 fatalities in Gaza and numerous injuries, escalating dramatically in 2024 with over 34,000 Palestinians killed and significant displacement due to ongoing hostilities (OCHA, 2023).³ Despite large number of fatalities and violation of international law (Genocide Convention), the term 'genocide' remains

contentious when applied to Gaza. As per UN, “Genocide is an act committed with the intent to destroy a national, ethnical, racial, or religious group, genocide is a severe accusation”. Critics argue that the humanitarian impact of Israeli military actions and the blockade constitutes genocide. Human Rights Watch and Amnesty International have documented disproportionate use of force, high civilian casualties, and destruction of infrastructure, suggesting potential war crimes or crimes against humanity (Pal, 2023).

Despite these concerns, major powers like the United States reject labelling the Gaza situation as genocide. U.S. officials argue that Israel's actions are self-defence against aggression from militant groups and that the situation, while dire, does not meet the legal definition of genocide.⁴ The U.S. has consistently vetoed UN resolutions critical of Israel and provided substantial military support, underscoring its strategic alliance with Israel. The selective use of the term ‘genocide’ by major powers highlights how geopolitical interests influence international responses. The U.S. recognition of the Armenian Genocide in 2021, amidst strained relations with Turkey, contrasts with its reluctance to apply the term to Gaza, driven by strategic interests rather than consistent legal standards. This pattern reveals the limitations of liberal internationalism and the dominance of realist principles in global politics.

Realism vs. Liberal Internationalism: Lessons from Historical Genocides

The Gaza crisis, along with other historical genocides, underscores significant lessons for international relations, particularly highlighting the limitations of liberal internationalism and the dominance of realist principles. The persistent influence of state interests and power politics often overshadows the principles of international law and humanitarianism. This realist analysis provides critical insights into the dynamics of international relations and suggests strategic measures for preventing and addressing genocides. The unwavering support of the United States for Israel, despite international condemnation of Israel's actions in Gaza, illustrates that strategic interests often take precedence over humanitarian considerations. The U.S. views Israel as a vital ally in a geopolitically volatile region, providing strategic military and intelligence advantages. This alignment underscores the realist perspective that national interests and security

considerations are paramount, often at the expense of human rights and international norms (Mearsheimer & Walt, 2007).

The inability of international organizations like the United Nations to enforce resolutions and take decisive action in Gaza results from power dynamics among member states. The veto power of permanent UN Security Council members, particularly the U.S., has repeatedly blocked resolutions critical of Israel. This dynamic illustrates how power politics can hinder collective action and supports the realist view that international organizations are often tools for the most powerful states to advance their own interests rather than impartial enforcers of international law (Smith, 2009). Powerful states manipulate international organizations to serve their interests, as seen in the U.S.'s efforts to discredit the Goldstone Report and prevent accountability for war crimes in Gaza. This manipulation undermines the credibility and effectiveness of these organizations, highlighting the realist critique of liberal internationalism's reliance on global institutions to maintain peace and order (Goldstone, 2009). The Armenian and Rwandan genocides further emphasize how geopolitical interests of major powers limit humanitarian responses and recognition of genocidal acts. During the Armenian Genocide, major powers were preoccupied with World War I, and post-war geopolitical considerations led to delayed recognition due to Turkey's strategic importance (Hovannisian, 1992; Winter, 2003). Similarly, the Rwandan Genocide saw a lack of intervention due to the political reluctance of major powers, with the U.S. wary of involvement post-Somalia and France prioritizing its interests in Rwanda (Power, 2002; Melvern, 2000).

For international organizations to be more effective in preventing genocides, they must enhance mechanisms for accountability and enforcement of international law. Reforms to decision-making processes, such as mitigating the influence of veto powers in the UN Security Council, could enable more impartial and decisive actions. Strengthening the role of smaller states and non-state actors in international diplomacy may also contribute to more balanced and effective interventions. To mitigate the influence of powerful states, international organizations should adopt measures that limit geopolitical manipulation. This could involve increasing transparency in decision-making processes and ensuring that humanitarian concerns take precedence over strategic

interests. By fostering a culture of accountability, international bodies can improve their credibility and effectiveness in addressing genocides. The selective use of the term 'genocide' by major powers highlights the need for consistent application of international legal standards. Establishing clear criteria and independent mechanisms for recognizing genocides can help prevent the politicization of the term. This consistency would reinforce the legitimacy of international interventions and contribute to the prevention and punishment of genocidal acts.

The realist analysis of the Gaza conflict and other historical genocides underscores the dominance of state interests and power politics in international relations. To effectively prevent and address genocides, the international community must enhance accountability, reduce geopolitical manipulation, and promote legal consistency. These measures can help align international actions with humanitarian principles, challenging the limitations of liberal internationalism and addressing the root causes of protracted conflicts.

Conclusion

This research paper has illustrated how the geopolitical interests of major powers have hindered the international response and recognition of genocides through the cases of the Armenian Genocide, the Rwandan Genocide, and the recent Gaza crisis. Our analysis shows that major powers have often misused their veto power in the United Nations Security Council to support their allies, thereby prioritizing national interests over international law and humanitarian principles. In the Armenian Genocide, geopolitical alliances and World War I preoccupations delayed recognition and response. During the Rwandan Genocide, reluctance from the United States and France to intervene was driven by their national interests, despite the evident need for humanitarian action. Similarly, the Gaza crisis highlights the United States' consistent use of its veto power to shield Israel, underscoring the realist view that state interests trump humanitarian considerations.

Our findings support the realist critique of liberal internationalism, emphasizing that state power and interests primarily drive international relations, often at the expense of justice and human rights. To effectively prevent and address genocides, we propose the establishment of a robust system that limits the veto power of major powers in cases of genocide and human rights

violations. Additionally, major powers must restrain their allies rather than shielding them from accountability. Therefore, to uphold international humanitarian law and prevent future genocides, reforms are needed to mitigate the undue influence of major powers and ensure a principled approach to global governance. This will better protect vulnerable populations and promote lasting peace and justice.

Notes

¹ United Nations. “Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide.” 1948. https://www.un.org/en/genocideprevention/documents/atrocities-crimes/Doc.1_Convention.

² Reuters. “US State Department Rejects Genocide Allegations in Gaza Conflict.” November 20, 2023. <https://www.reuters.com/world/us-politics/us-state-department-rejects-genocide-allegations-gaza-conflict-2023-11-20/>.

³ United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), “Casualties,” OCHA, accessed May 10, 2024, <https://www.ochaopt.org/data/casualties>.

⁴ Reuters. “US State Department Rejects Genocide Allegations in Gaza Conflict.” November 20, 2023. <https://www.reuters.com/world/us-politics/us-state-department-rejects-genocide-allegations-gaza-conflict-2023-11-20/>.

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